

Blended learning effectiveness: Teacher's and student's perception of English for specific purpose classroom of Pns, Lumhs Jamshoro

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Abstract: The current study focuses on the blended learning effectiveness as perception by teachers and students in an ESP classroom. To assess the effectiveness and perception, the current study used a mixed method technique. Quantitative data was obtained using a questionnaire, while qualitative data was acquired using semi-structured interviews and convenient sampling. The findings emphasized the need for new technological aids to boost b-learning in ESP, as well as its emotional components, impediments, and application suggestions.

Keywords: Blended learning, Technolog, Teacher's and Student's Perception, ESP.

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Introduction

The English language has grown in importance and depth in almost every element of life. Globalization and the steady development in international communication in various areas are increasing the need for ESP, particularly in countries where English is taught as a foreign language. Because Pakistan is a developing country with English as a second language, generic English is prioritized over ESP. Though it is well-known fact ESP training is quite beneficial in preparing employees for their specific employment.

The concept of blended learning has been around for a while, but its language had not been fully defined until around the turn of the century. Blended learning may be defined as a system that combines traditional classroom learning with online instruction (Graham, 2013). This necessitates a combination of on-the-job and online training centered on machines (Wang, 2011). The mix can comprise a variety of event-based activities such as physical classrooms, internet-based learning, group learning, symmetric video conferencing and preparation, or simultaneous awareness teaching (Graham, 2013).

To satisfy individual student requirements, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instructors must master multidisciplinary knowledge, as evidenced by the necessity to combine linguistics with content (Luo & Garner, 2017). In Pakistan, where English is taught as a foreign language, these lecturers encounter a variety of challenges. Even though their degrees are unrelated to ESP, students nevertheless need to study new English-related content according to a specific learning discipline for context-based learners. The majority of them intended to teach English at junior high and senior high schools after they graduated from the English Education Department. This suggests that both teachers and students are cooperating to accomplish specific goals, such as ensuring Basic English communication, applying ESP in a novel situation, and getting ready for ESP tests. As a result, English instruction in ESP situations is required not just to prepare students for standardized examinations but also to improve their English proficiency in real-world conversation (Widodo, 2017).

Pakistan had a language policy difficulty when it obtained independence in 1947, according to a historical look at the country's language policies (Haq, 1993). Urdu was declared as a national language, but one local language from each province was designated as the official provincial language to keep the government working smoothly, while English retained the official language. In the educational context, two languages predominated. Urdu has been the primary language of instruction since the year 2000. In 1948, particularly at higher levels, English was the medium of teaching. There were Urdu and English language schools all around the country. As a result of this event, two educational systems and, as a result, two classes of people emerged: the upper class for superior jobs and the lower class for lower occupations (Ibid., pp. 13-14)

B-learning is a novel teaching approach in ESP training that promotes autonomous English learning abilities by integrating interactive assignments into a virtual classroom environment to increase students' learning engagement and information interchange (Chen, Liu, Lin, & Wang, 2019). It is now referred to as ESP instruction transformation, which aids learners in becoming active and self-sufficient in their mastery of English skills.

According to studies (Chirimbu, 2014; Mulyadi, Hersulastuti, & Purnama, 2019), the use of bl in ESP classrooms improves semi-significant learners' attitudes and motivation toward learning English as a foreign language. Bl (Lalima & Dangwal, 2017; Kuruçova, Medová, & Tirpakova, 2018), also has a significant impact on students' English proficiency beyond online or conventional learning methods. Additionally, bl has been asserted that it can address challenges with online education such as student engagement and instructing lower-level students who have weak English abilities (Arslanyilmaz, 2012; Iveson, 2015). According to Vijayakumar & Viswanathan (2018), this approach fared better than online learning at guaranteeing students' task completion. This research will focus on the efficacy of blended learning in an English classroom for a specific goal. Most instructors, it has been discovered, are hesitant to adopt blended learning owing to a lack of training and internet access. The old conventional process takes a long time. Learners' education is hampered by a lack of resources, training, and awareness. The efficacy of blended learning in the English for Specific Purposes classroom will be investigated in this project. This research will look at how students and instructors perceive blended learning in English for Specific Purposes classroom.

Objective

- 1: Investigate the effectiveness of blended learning in an ESP classroom.
- 2: To explore learner's and teacher's perceptions towards the effectiveness of blended learning strategies in an ESP classroom

Research Methodology

The nature of the research used for this study would be mixed methodology. Mixed method analysis includes both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The blend of quantitative and qualitative methodologies throughout numerous stages of the study involves the philosophical concerns that influence the path of data collection and analysis. A single study or set of studies, focuses on gathering, analyzing, and integrating quantitative and qualitative data. Its core premise is that integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies yields a more comprehensive knowledge of research topics than either strategy alone (Creswell, Clark, 2007).

Explanatory inquiry is a method for analyzing phenomena that have never been studied previously or have never been well explained. Its main objective is to provide us with knowledge about potential locations for a small amount of data. This approach enables the researcher to get a broad understanding before using research to assist them to get closer to the problems that require future attention. Its goal is to determine what and why anything is worthwhile to study. An efficient way to get comparable data from a large number of individuals is through the use of questionnaires. In contrast, questionnaires can only produce reliable and relevant results if the questions are precise and all respondents answer them uniformly. The questionnaire items that have been used and validated by various researchers. To gather the information, semi-structured interviews would be done. The study focuses on the most common sort of semi-structured interview – individual, face-to-face, in-depth interviews – for qualitative analysis.

Data Analysis

Kruskal – Wallis H Test

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	SCORE
Kruskal-Wallis H	25.955
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: PARTICIPANTS	

Table 1: Kruskal – Wallis H Test

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there is a statistically significant difference. If P is below then .05 there is a statistically significant difference.

Factor Analysis

A method of data reduction is factor analysis. By condensing or summarizing a vast number of variables, factor analysis may portray them as various factors or components. The purpose of a factor analysis is to condense the data from many different variables into a small number of components.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Activities	Component			Student Interest
		Course Content	Student Performance	Teaching Methodology	
A1	.833				
A2	.645				
A5	.831				
A7	.606				
A9	.806				
A10	.833				
CC11		.828			
CC12		.928			
CC13		.930			
CC14		.805			
CC15		.581			
TM19				.910	
TM20				.867	
SI28					.913
SI30					.644
SP34			.888		
SP35			.881		
SP42			.715		
SP44			.886		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Table 2: Factor Analysis RCM

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Activites	100	1.00	5.00	3.5450	1.01914
CC	100	1.00	5.00	3.5520	.93295
TM	100	1.00	5.00	3.6700	1.14420
SI	100	1.00	5.00	3.2550	1.19023
SP	100	1.00	5.00	3.6125	1.19309
Valid N (listwise)	100				

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

This table shows that the average mean was 3.5 for all the remaining items of the questionnaire. The goal of this research is to see how successful blended learning is in English for Specific Purposes in classrooms. The study's goal is to look at how learners and instructors interact in a blended learning English for Specific Purpose classroom.

Student's Interview

S.no	Response from Participants	Codes
1	Participant 1: we get low attention spam from our teacher and it makes us less attentive in the classroom	Low attention Confidence level

	<p>Participant 1: BL gives us a lot of chances to participate in the classroom, it makes us more attentive and increases our confidence level and skills.</p> <p>Participant 2: enhances our skills through multimedia presentations in the online or physical classroom</p> <p>Participant 2: Through physical classroom multimedia presentations we learn a lot due to our physical presence. We learn easily through seeing rather than listening. But sometimes our energy is also deprived due to the physical classroom.</p> <p>Participant 3: It enhances my skills through the multimedia presentation in which I participate and interact with my classmates and teacher.</p> <p>Participant 3: Physical classroom is essential but it should be with blended learning. It enhances my skills and my confidence level too.</p> <p>Participant 4: Blended learning increase a lot of our skills it motivates us a lot in the classroom. It creates competition among students and increases interest. It helps to increase our skills, increase our focus and make us more competitive.</p> <p>Participant 5: Blended learning is very important in enhancing my skills during class. When the teacher bring different activities in the classroom which were engaging us in the classroom likewise the medical vocabulary and after describing the whole topic with the help of multimedia and then she give us a quiz-based task that helped me to remember the important vocabulary.</p>	<p>Skills</p> <p>Physical Participation</p> <p>Participation</p> <p>Different Activities</p> <p>Motivation</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>Participant 1: more attentive due to our physical presence.</p>	<p>Attentive</p> <p>Technological Issues</p> <p>Interaction</p>

<p>Participant 1: In an online classroom we face a lot of online issues, connectivity, lack of attention, and a non-serious attitude from us.</p> <p>Participant 2: In a physical classroom, we can interact with our teacher easily because we are attentive in the classroom. In online classes, we face problems due to technology and the internet we cannot interact easily due to bad internet coverage and communication.</p> <p>Participant 2: same in a physical classroom we don't face any issues of communication and interaction. I think if there is a large classroom it should be divided into two sections. It will help in interaction and classroom learning.</p> <p>Participant 3: In classroom learning, we are more attentive toward learning because we are physically present in the classroom. In an Online classroom, we are less attentive because of the home environment and lack of interest.</p> <p>Participant 4: Classroom learning is more effective in our context rather than online learning. In online learning, we face a lot of issues with internet connectivity, not enough knowledge about online classrooms, and few poor students and families even don't afford 24 hours internet connectivity and modern devices. Blended learning should be based on classroom learning and multimedia aid should be available.</p> <p>Participant 5: The major difference between physical and online classrooms is the hindrance of technology as we students belong to different areas of rural Sindh. As I belong to tharparker so I traveled 5 to 6 km in search of an internet connection for taking online classes and participating in class but due to network</p>	<p>Lack of interest</p> <p>Large classroom</p>
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	<p>issues, I faced difficulties in attending class. For me, a physical classroom is far better than an online classroom.</p>	
3	<p>Participant 1: the task of summary writings and due to marks and assignments we need to complete our writing tasks.</p> <p>Participant 1: Classroom presentations (via A/v aid) on different topics, and group discussions these were the activities</p> <p>Participant 2: performed activities via giving presentations through multimedia, and classroom activities by certain role play related to the topic. We also performed certain acts related to our medical field of nursing in the ESP classroom and watched videos related to the topic.</p> <p>Participant 3: We perform some task-based activities like online group discussions, posters, debates, and role-based, classroom presentations which save a lot of time and increase classroom interaction and sometimes video related to any specific topic.</p> <p>Participant 4: We give presentations, group tasks, extempore presentations, assignments, and summary writings. Sometimes we are given tasks related to the medical field so we use the internet and make multimedia presentations for the classroom.</p> <p>Extempore tasks increase lot my skills and motivate me a lot in classroom learning.</p> <p>Participant 5: In the blended learning classroom we are performing different activities with the help of multimedia I give presentations in the classroom, and the second activity is watching videos related to nursing, we give extempore speeches in the classroom.</p>	<p>Writing tasks</p> <p>Presentations</p> <p>Group discussions</p> <p>Multimedia (A/v aid)</p> <p>Activities</p>
4	<p>Participant 1: sometimes face a time problem where I don't have enough time to complete a given task due to commotion.</p>	<p>Time management</p> <p>Fewer opportunities</p> <p>Load shedding</p>

	<p>Participant 1: challenges I face are fewer opportunities for equal participation and sometimes even nepotism.</p> <p>Participant 2: In blended learning class we face the issue of load shedding and the internet, and sometimes when there are back-to-back classrooms it deprives our energy of us and our performance.</p> <p>Participant 3: Mostly I face the challenge of load shedding and no internet service. Sometimes students don't have enough knowledge about these digital devices. Few students don't have proper access to the internet and computer.</p> <p>Participant 3: Furthermore we don't have enough knowledge about these applications, at the beginning I face a little bit of a problem understanding and using applications. Mostly I face these issues in online classrooms.</p> <p>Participant 4: We face the issue of a large classroom. It is a challenge for the teacher to how the lecture will be delivered by the teacher. The teachers should deliver a lecture in a way that every student should be attentive. A teacher should use more blended learning methodologies in the classroom.</p> <p>Participant 5: Technology issues, shortage of electricity, and continuously sitting in the classroom.</p>	<p>No internet service</p> <p>Large classroom</p> <p>Technology issues</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Participant 1: it increases the competition among class fellows it provides us with a certain road map and we prepare ourselves according to that road map</p> <p>Participant 1: We go home and prepare ourselves for the tasks and activities for the next day's classroom.</p> <p>Participant 2: We can learn a lot of things and skills through a blended learning classroom than a physical classroom. It saves a</p>	<p>Competition</p> <p>Save time</p> <p>Prefer Blended learning</p> <p>Increases interest</p> <p>Engage student</p>

	<p>lot of time for both us and our teacher by writing on board or copies.</p> <p>Participant 3: In blended learning in the physical classroom I prefer a lot. In that classroom, I'm more attentive and active, and with the help of blended learning different activities, tasks, and lecture delivery increases my interest in learning.</p> <p>Participant 4: I prefer Blended learning in the classroom. It engages every student and gives them more chances to students to participate. It motivates and increases students' skills to participate and become more attentive students in the classroom.</p> <p>Participant 5: I prefer blended learning in the classroom because it helps me to understand the lecture adequately by using multimedia content, and talking with other university students on the same topic. On the other hand in the traditional classroom teacher explains and writes the main points on the board so either we listen or write or understand what she is explaining to us. So it is difficult for me to understand and write the main points in my notebook at the same moment. That's why I prefer blended learning in the classroom.</p>	
<p>6</p>	<p>Participant 1: prefer a physical learning classroom, not an online learning classroom because I'm more attentive in the physical classroom than online. Even most of the students are not attentive in the online classroom.</p> <p>Participant 1: classroom should be divided into two sections it will give the chance of equal opportunity and participation.</p> <p>Participant 2: I would prefer a physical classroom, not the traditional but a combination of blended learning. In online classes, we face a lot of issues.</p>	<p>Attentive in Physical Not attentive to Online Equal participation Help in Assessment Prefer physical classroom</p>

	<p>Participant 3: I prefer physical learning to blended learning. In physical learning, as a student, I'm more attentive and it will also help my teacher with assessment. Blended learning tasks and activities can more easily implement in the physical classroom rather the online.</p> <p>Participant 4: I prefer an online classroom but if students have internet connectivity, proper setup to attend classroom, devices, and student proper attention. Government should also play its role to support students. Students should be engaged in the online classroom.</p> <p>Participant 5: I prefer blended learning in a physical classroom as it helps and motivates students to participate in class activities and enhance their knowledge and it saves a lot of time also in understanding the different concepts.</p>	
7	<p>Participant 2: I think on daily basis there should be an assessment of our quizzes and there should be the proper arrangements for A/v aid.</p> <p>Participant 3: We should have some extempore presentations, and group works in the classroom. I would suggest that we should learn different strategies and methodologies to increase students' motivation.</p> <p>Participant 4: I think students and teachers both should be trained and become familiar with online learning. It saves a lot of time and money.</p> <p>Participant 5: If our teacher adds 10 minutes activity on daily basis in a blended learning classroom which is based upon the MCQs quiz along with the assessment of that quiz test then it will help us a lot in learning and improving our knowledge day</p>	<p>Assessment</p> <p>Quizzes</p> <p>Extempore</p> <p>Presentations</p> <p>Training</p> <p>Activities daily</p> <p>MCQS</p>

	<p>by day and at the day of exams we students would not be worried about MCQs.</p>	
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Table 4: Student’s Interview

Teacher’s Interview

S.no	Response from Participants	Codes
1	<p>T1: Due to covid 19 blended learning provides benefits for my class. In the online classroom, I also use blended learning techniques and daily basis activity in the form of a quiz, MCQs, and short answers which help students to improve their skills. The lesson I learned from blended learning is that for better results I need a lesson plan for my class as well a daily assessment of my students is very much necessary.</p> <p>T2: Being a teacher it is always been a tricky task to engage students because their concentration can be diverted by the littlest of things. I used to plan my lessons in a way in which all the students were physically involved in the learning process. For instance, for the English for medical, I used to assign my students a skit task in which they were supposed to create a skit surrounding the storyline of their syllabus. Noticeable and appreciable changes were seen through this pattern of learning because it was a very fun and productive way of explaining and reading.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Activities 2. Assessment 3. Learning 4. Engage 5. Productive
2	<p>T1: Actual aims to combine the strengths of both transitional and online learning methods to give learners a more engaging learning experience for the specific subject. Blended learning can help teachers to provide several formats of learning material. Then it can increase student motivation and they can get new experiences in learning.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage the learner 2. Helpful 3. Motivation 4. Creative

	<p>T2: Blended learning was very helpful for me because I had a class of those students who were extremely creative but did not know how to utilize that creativity. Peer checking and flipped homework were one of the results-worthy techniques that have helped me a lot.</p>	
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Table 5: Teacher’s Interview

Conclusion

The current study examined instructors' and students' perspectives on critical elements that might enhance blended learning in ESP education, such as understanding the advantages of bl, the challenges of putting it into practice, and suggestions for making it effective. This study found several pedagogical and practical implications, with TELL workshops and training, cyberinfrastructure, and software use being the most crucial factors in enhancing ESP instructors' instructional methods. The freedom to access and participate in academic tasks that enable learners to utilize the knowledge at their own pace and learn creative language from a range of sources were also identified as the most advantageous aspects of bl. Furthermore, lecturers proposed that the learning strategy be implemented by examining students' preparedness to study using technology, fostering autonomous learning, raising their interest and learning motivation, and improving lecturers' technical literacy. In the meanwhile, problems with e-learning access control, poor class management, professors who are resistant to employing technology, and inconsistent internet connectivity have all been noted.

In the example of qualitative data acquired from students to investigate the learner's perspective of the efficiency of BL in an ESP classroom, it was discovered that when students participate in BL, their skills in the classroom improve. On the other hand, owing to the huge classroom, internet challenges, limited opportunities, load shedding, and time management, they confront a few technical issues and classroom management in the BL. They take part in classroom activities such as writing assignments, presentations, group discussions, and multimedia (A/V assistance), among others. They are also motivated, involved, and prefer BL in a physical classroom.

In the instance of qualitative data acquired from instructors to investigate their perceptions of the usefulness of BL in ESP classrooms, it was discovered that BL engages and encourages learners in the classroom, allowing us to involve them in activities and assessments. In BL, they are dealing with a lack of instruction on how to handle technology in the classroom, which has harmed their connection. They employ flipped classrooms in the classroom, incorporating social media and project-based learning. BL offers flexibility and improvement, yet it is plagued with technological difficulties.

The idea of blended learning can help instructors accomplish their goals more successfully. As long as they have access to the Internet, it enables students to hone and practice their English outside of the classroom, anytime and whenever they choose. Additionally, it enables children to repeat lessons without worrying about criticism or pressure. According to the results of this study, this type of blended learning has been shown to enhance student learning. Students can participate in self-directed learning and knowledge transfer when e-learning is integrated into classroom education

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